

Surrogate-based modeling for investigating and controlling the response of an axisymmetric jet to harmonic forcing

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We investigate the response of an axisymmetric turbulent jet at $Re = 10.000$ to a superposition of two azimuthally distributed harmonic forcing signals. This forcing is achieved by means of eight independently controlled loudspeakers at the turbulent jet's exit. The forcing amplitude is limited to 2% of the total mass flow of the main jet and is kept constant for all measurements. The objective is to reduce the centerline velocity of the turbulent jet. A reduction in the centerline velocity implies higher entrainment of the turbulent jet, which is of interest for mixing purposes. We investigate different forcing structures with an axial or helical shape and superpose these signals. In the resulting parameter space, a global minimum is sought. This global optimization is performed by identifying a surrogate model, optimized to reduce the model uncertainty by iteratively measuring the point in parameter space with the highest model uncertainty. A global minimum is then identified from the generated surrogate model. In contrast to other optimization techniques, this approach yields a surrogate model that delivers accurate information not only in the proximity of the minimum but in a much broader parameter range, which aids in understanding the influence of each parameter on the jet response. The results for a superposition of two axisymmetric forcing signals or one axisymmetric and one spinning forcing signals approximately match known results from the literature. In addition, we investigate the superposition of two counter-spinning helical forcings, resulting in a lower centerline velocity than the other measured values. This identified optimal forcing is then validated experimentally, and the jet response is further investigated by visualizing the flow with a laser sheet.

I. Introduction

THE turbulent round jet is one of the most canonical configurations of a shear flow, it has been the subject of many academic studies since the beginning of the last century [1], and has direct technical applications, e.g., in

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gas turbine combustion [2]. In addition to the properties of the time-averaged flow field, the coherent structures that occur in the shear layer between the emerging jet and the surrounding fluid are of high interest in research [3]. The ring-shaped vortices which naturally form as a result of Kelvin-Helmholtz-type instabilities, lead to entrainment of the surrounding fluid and mixing with the jet. This results in a growth of the shear layers in the flow direction, which merge into a fully turbulent flow with a decay of the axial velocity downstream of the potential core [4]. Due to the significant influence of these coherent structures on the mean flow properties, numerous investigations cover active control of shear layer instabilities [5]. The shear layer's high susceptibility to disturbances in the vicinity of the nozzle lip enables highly efficient flow control measures to be applied [6]. For harmonic monofrequent axisymmetric excitation, forcing frequencies close to the dominant natural frequency of the unforced flow have been found to be particularly efficient [3, 7]. The superposition of several excitation frequencies can lead to non-linear interactions between the excited structures, which significantly change the mean flow field [8]. For example, the non-linear coupling mechanism of vortices induced by two axisymmetric forcing signals at sub-harmonic frequency was investigated theoretically in Refs. [8, 9] and experimentally in [10]. Forcing patterns with a non-zero azimuthal wavenumber can be generated by controlling the phase delay of multiple actuators distributed around the nozzle. Interaction between helical forcing patterns were studied in Ref. [11]. Significant azimuthal distortion of the mean flow from the combination of helical and axisymmetric excitation was shown experimentally in Ref. [12]. A particular jet structure, known as blooming jet, was found in Ref. [13] as a result of combined axial and helical harmonic forcing. To summarize, the combination of different actuation signals allows one to strongly influence the mean flow by means of small, targeted disturbances of the shear layer.

Finding optimal actuation patterns, for example to maximize mixing is, however, a non-trivial task. When superposing two (or more) harmonic signals, the number of actuation parameters that need to be specified becomes large, since, for each signal the azimuthal mode number, the frequency, the amplitude, and the phase offset to the other signals need to be set. Already for a superposition of two signals, this results in an seven-dimensional parameter space. Comprehensive experimental investigation of these high-dimensional parameter spaces is thus usually unfeasible. Flow simulations based on the time-averaged equations are computationally inexpensive and generally also allow larger parameter studies. However, these do not permit dynamic considerations, and therefore cannot capture oscillating excitation. Time-resolved simulations like DNS or LES are, on the other hand, prohibitively expensive for large parameter studies. One approach to obtaining optimal excitation strategies with less effort is the use of machine learning (ML) methods. Evolutionary strategies have been combined with simulations of jet flow in Refs. [14, 15] to identify optimal forcing parameters. Genetic programming has been applied to identify closed-loop control laws, which link flow actuation to hot wire probe signals to improve mixing [16, 17]. Although the authors in Ref. [16] conclude that a closed-loop control of the actuation does not further improve the mixing compared to optimized open loop forcing, both approaches were able to identify favorable forcing patterns without the use of physical knowledge. Other machine learning methods

which do not rely on evolutionary approaches have also found application in flow control [18]. In this work, Bayesian Optimization (BO) is used to optimize the forcing in a jet flow experiment with the goal of improved mixing of the jet with the surrounding fluid [19]. In BO the functional relation between input variables (forcing parameters in the present case) and function values (measured flow properties) is approximated using Gaussian Process (GP) regression [20, 21]. In an iterative process, the GP approximation is used to choose the next input sample for evaluation (measurement). The sampling is controlled by using an acquisition function that combines the prediction value and the prediction uncertainty of the GP. After the function value is acquired for the chosen sample, the GP is updated with the newly added training data and the process starts over. In classical BO, the aim is to find a minimum of the unknown function within a minimal number of function calls. For this purpose different acquisition functions have been suggested, aiming to strike a balance between exploration and exploitation [22, 23]. In this work, we pursue a different approach. Instead of using the BO method to identify a minimum in the first place, we aim to train the GP such that it provides reliable predictions for measurement values across the entire parameter space in order to use it as a surrogate model for the test rig. This is achieved by sampling parameters for which the prediction uncertainty is highest, i.e. by choosing the model uncertainty itself as acquisition function. The surrogate-model based approach allows us to gain further insight of the jet response. For example, it enables a detailed sensitivity analysis in addition to identifying one optimal forcing pattern. The latter is done a posteriori by a minimum search on the surrogate’s response to determine its global minimum. A simplicial homology global optimization is used for this purpose [24]. Once a minimum is identified from the surrogate model, a more detailed experimental investigation of the turbulent jet, forced at the optimized conditions is carried out.

II. Experimental Setup

This study was carried out by adapting the experimental setup originally developed by Oberleithner et al.[25], but without the use of the swirl generators. The setup generates an axisymmetric turbulent jet, operated with a Reynolds number of $Re = 10,000$. In Fig. 1a, a schematic drawing of the turbulent jet setup is shown. A thermal mass flow controller regulates the air flux, which is then introduced to a plenum. The air is passed through honeycombs, which serve as flow straighteners, before it reaches the contracting nozzle. The test rig is equipped with eight independently controlled loudspeakers whose waveguides end at slots near the nozzle output. Driving the speakers with harmonic signals generates pulsed zero-net-mass-flow jets that actuate the shear layer at the nozzle lip.

As done in other studies [16, 17], we utilize the fact that optimal mixing is associated with maximum entrainment of the surrounding fluid and thus with maximum growth of the shear layer width in the flow directions. This leads to a shortened potential core and a faster decay of mean center line velocity. The response of the jet to different forcing patterns can therefore be characterized by measurements of the time-averaged center-line velocity at a fixed location. For this purpose, a Pitot tube is installed at a distance of seven nozzle diameters ($D = 51$ mm) downstream the nozzle outlet, as can be seen in Fig. 1b. This position is chosen to be downstream of the potential core in order to be sensitive

to acoustic forcing at the jet outlet. The pressure values of the Pitot tube are measured by a Baratron capacitance manometer and are converted into velocity values, representing a continuous indicator of the forcing effectiveness.

The jet flow is actuated by superposing two azimuthally distributed harmonic signals at the eight independently controlled loudspeakers. The i th harmonic component of the forcing signal at the n th loudspeaker reads:

$$F_{n,i}(t) = A_i \sin(2\pi f_i t + \phi_i + \frac{2\pi n}{8} m_i) \quad (1)$$

with A denoting the amplitude of the forcing, chosen to be $\leq 2\%$ of the main jet mass momentum; n an integer ranging from $n \in [1, 8]$, denoting the number of the loudspeaker, so that $\frac{2\pi n}{8}$ denotes the angle at which the n th loudspeaker is placed; f denoting the forcing frequency, fixed in the range $f \in [5, 400]$ Hz; ϕ denoting a phase with values in the range $[0, 2\pi)$; and m an integer denoting the azimuthal mode number. Given that our setup comprises eight equispaced loudspeakers, we can excite azimuthal waveforms with azimuthal numbers m in the range $m \in [-3, 3]$. A multi-modal forcing signal is then constructed by superposing each loudspeaker with two harmonic signals:

$$F_n(t) = \sum_{i=1}^2 F_{n,i}(t). \quad (2)$$

The maximum forcing amplitude, $A_{\max} = \sum_i A_i$, is fixed at a constant value that is set not to surpass 2% of the mass momentum of the turbulent jet. This is because an investigation that included the overall forcing amplitude A_{\max} as a degree of freedom resulted in a trivial solution, showing that the centerline velocity decreases monotonically with increasing forcing amplitude. With increasing amplitude, the optima tend to brute force the jet into a swirling motion

Fig. 1 Experimental setup of the turbulent jet. (a): Schematic drawing of the entire facility, adopted from [25]. (b): Detail on the positioning of the probe of the loudspeakers at the exit plane, highlighted with red markers.

for the spinning modes. To prevent this trivial solution, we fix the forcing amplitude, but the amplitude ratio between the two superposed harmonic signals is varied. By defining the ratio parameter $A_s \in [0, 1]$, the following relations define the amplitudes of the signals A_1 and A_2 :

$$A_1 = A_s \cdot A_{\max}, \quad A_2 = (1 - A_s) \cdot A_{\max}. \quad (3)$$

III. Automation and optimization

The experiment is automatized and controlled via LabVIEW software, which handles the described input variables and records the velocity measurement at the end of the potential core. For the communication between the LabVIEW program and the Python-based optimization algorithm, a file-share approach is used. An automated experiment is initiated once a new set-file with input variables is generated from the optimization method. After the experiment, the measured velocity value is stored back into a read-file, which activates a new iteration of the optimization algorithm. The optimization routine is described in the next section.

The optimization algorithm is developed using the Toolbox SMT [26]. This toolbox handles the model generation and the prediction of the model for the absolute value and the variance. The surrogate model is chosen to be a Kriging model [27] with a Matérn 5/2 correlation function [21]. The algorithm is schematically described in Alg. 1. The optimization is initialized by measuring an initial amount of sampling points n_{init} sourced from a Latin Hyper Cube sampling [28]. Then the algorithm creates the surrogate model and searches for the point with the highest predicted variance within the given domain. The automatized experiment then measures this point. This process is repeated until a maximum n_{iter} amount of iterations is reached. Last, a global and local minimum search with a simplicial homology global optimization [24] is performed on the generated surrogate model. For the studies in this work, the $n_{init} = 100$ and $n_{iter} = 650$ are chosen for a four-dimensional parameter space.

Algorithm 1 Surrogate Model Algorithm for a *a posteriori* minimisation

Initialization: Generate an initial set of measurement points N_{init} on the given domain by using a Latin Hypercube Sampling and measure these points.

while $n < n_{iter}$ **do**

Step 1: Generate the surrogate model.

Step 2: Generate candidate points and let the surrogate model predict their variance. Choose the candidate point with the highest value as the next iteration point.

Step 3: Measure the selected point.

end while

Minimum Search: Perform a *a posteriori* global and local minimum search with a simplicial homology global optimization algorithm on the surrogate model.

IV. Results

In the following, first the results of the optimizations of the surrogate model for varying modal forcings are displayed. Then some of the found minima are further investigated by utilizing flow visualization.

A. Results of the surrogate models for varying modal overlays

We apply three different superpositions of azimuthally distributed harmonic forcings to the turbulent jet in the following. We fixed the maximal amplitude, the phase value of the first signal, and the mode value for the two superposed harmonic frequencies, resulting in four optimization parameters, namely f_1, f_2, A_s, ϕ_2 . We perform three sets of experiments in which we superpose (i) two axial modes ($m = 0$), (ii) two helical modes ($m = \pm 1$), or (iii) an axial and a helical mode. The details of each optimization are displayed in Tab. 1.

Experiment	m_1	m_2	f_1 (Hz)	f_2 (Hz)	A_s %	ϕ_2 (deg)	n_{\max}	u_{diff}
1. Two axial modes	0	0	5-400	5-400	5-95	0-360	750	16.54%
2. One axial and one helical mode	0	1	5-400	5-400	5-95	0-360	750	28.05%
3. Two counter spinning helical modes	-1	1	5-400	5-400	5-95	0-360	750	29.5%

Table 1 Overview of the conducted optimizations, the boundary conditions of the parameters are kept constant for all three optimizations.

For the results shown in the following, the difference of the velocity at the probe in comparison to the velocity without forcing is displayed and calculated as follows:

$$u_{\text{diff}} = 1 - \frac{u_{\text{predict}}}{u_{\text{base}}}. \quad (4)$$

For the found minima, the values are measured to validate the results of the surrogate model. These experimentally acquired values are labeled $u_{\text{diff,exp}}$ and are calculated analogously. The optimization goal is to increase the mixing of the turbulent jet compared to the unforced case. The identified minimum for each considered pair of forcings is displayed in the following subsections, and a variation of the parameters around the found minima with the highest predicted centerline velocity reduction is performed. This variation is performed to investigate further the influence of each freedom parameter on the result. For a better comparison with other studies, the frequencies found by the optimization are converted into the Strouhal number by the expression:

$$\text{St} = \frac{fD}{u}, \quad (5)$$

with u denoting the mean flow velocity at the outlet plane of the jet. Based on the mass flow, which is set to be $\dot{m} = 26.6$ kg/h for our experiments, we obtain a characteristic velocity of $u = 3.04$ m/s.

The optimization of the surrogate model is performed with the full range of 0 - 1 for the amplitude ratio. For

the minimum search performed after the optimization, a constraint of 5% to the boundary is implemented to exclude possible solutions that include only a single modal forcing.

1. Overlay of two axial forcings

In this section, we display the experiment with an overlay of two axial forcings, implying two harmonic signals with azimuthal mode numbers $m_i = 0$. The optimization results of the first three minima are displayed in Tab. 2.

Nr.	f_1 (Hz)	St_1	f_2 (Hz)	St_2	A_s %	ϕ_2 (deg)	u_{diff}	$u_{diff, exp}$
1a	42.8	0.7170	22.2	0.3719	94.5	237	17.6	11.9
1b	42.8	0.7170	23.4	0.3920	92.2	180	16.9	13.3
1c	49.2	0.8242	307.6	5.1532	86.9	67.5	14.5	13.3

Table 2 First three minima obtained from the surrogate model for $m_1 = 0$, $m_2 = 0$ and the corresponding experimental values.

The minimum Nr. 1a results in a high forcing amplitude split, with the first forcing signal having $A_1 \approx 0.95A_{max}$ and a frequency f_1 of 42.8 Hz, whereas the second overlaid forcing signal has an amplitude of only 5 % of the total signal, and a frequency $f_2 = 22.2$ Hz. The resulting ratio of the two frequencies is approximately 2. The second local minimum, Nr. 1b, results in a similar forcing amplitude split, with approximately 92 % of the total amplitude in the first signal and 8 % in the second. The frequencies of both forcing signals are comparable to those of the minimum Nr. 1a, with only a slight variation for the f_2 frequency. The main difference to minimum Nr. 1a is the phase difference between the two overlaid signals. For minimum Nr. 1a it is $\phi_2 = 237^\circ$, instead, for the minimum Nr. 1b, it is 180° . The minimum Nr. 1c results in a forcing frequency for the first signal of $f_1 = 49.2$ Hz, similar to those of the other two minima, but has instead a much higher frequency for the overlaid second signal, with $f_2 = 307.6$ Hz. The second signal has an amplitude share of approximately 13 % of the total amplitude. The increase in amplitude share for the minimum Nr. 1c may be due to the increased power demand of the loudspeakers for higher frequencies to achieve comparable mass flows to lower frequencies.

In minima Nr. 1a & Nr. 1b both the frequencies and the amplitude ratio are approximately identical. Nevertheless, the phase has changed. For two overlaid harmonic signals, it can be shown that the response depends on the phase difference between the signals only if the ratio between the frequencies of the two signals is a rational number [29]. This can be considered the case here since the ratio between the two frequencies is close to 2. The two minima also share the same, with the lowest frequency $f_2 \approx 23$ Hz resulting in a St of 0.37. By recalling that the natural Strouhal number for an axisymmetric turbulent jet is $St \approx 0.3$ [30], we can see that one of the frequencies identified by the optimization algorithm is close to the natural frequency of the unforced jet. At this resonance condition, even a low amount of force is sufficient to strongly affect the shear layer structure of the turbulent jet. The third minimum for this condition, Nr. 1c, results in a different forcing of the second frequency $f_2 = 307$ Hz, corresponding to a frequency ratio compared to the

minima Nr. 1a & Nr. 1b of 13.3. Although this minimum has parameters that are much different from those of the other two identified minima, which are close to resonance conditions, it still results in an experimentally determined reduction in centerline velocity comparable to those of the other minima. We note that for all three local minima found in this experiment, the largest share of the amplitude is associated with a forcing frequency of approximately 45 Hz, corresponding to approximately twice the natural frequency of the turbulent jet. This indicates that the jet does not only significantly respond to a forcing frequency close to the natural frequency of the turbulent jet, but also at other non-trivial frequencies, and that our optimization algorithm is able to identify this non-trivial optimal forcing conditions. On a last note, we observe that the experimentally validated results do not show the same reduction in centerline velocity for the three minima. The reduction in centerline velocity is lower and ordered differently. This is especially the case for the minimum Nr. 1c, which, on the surrogate model, results in a lower reduction in centerline velocity and, instead, in the experimentally measured values, shows a comparable result to the minimum Nr. 1b. This indicates that the prediction quality of the surrogate model is not precise enough to determine accurate absolute figures for the minima, and a validation of the found local minima is necessary.

Fig. 2 Global minimum (black cross) of the surrogate model for $m_1 = 0$, $m_2 = 0$ with $Re = 10,000$ and a maximum forcing of $A_{max} = 2\%$. The planes are a cut through the minimum that is located at $f_1 = 42.8$ Hz, $f_2 = 22.2$ Hz, $A_s = 94.5\%$, $\phi_2 = 237^\circ$ with a velocity reduction at the centerline of $u_{diff} = 17.6\%$.

The global minimum of the surrogate model (Nr. 1a) is now further investigated. In Fig. 2, we show the variation of the optimization cost function around the parameters at which the global minimum is found. The identified global

minimum on the surrogate model (minimum Nr. 1a) shows that the share of the possible forcing amplitude between the two signals is split unevenly. The signal with frequency $f_1 \approx 43$ Hz has an amplitude $A_s \approx 95\%$, showing that the first forcing signal is dominant over the overlaid second one. The first frequency f_1 is approximately a factor of 1.93 higher than the second frequency. This result is comparable with the findings of [12], where the frequency ratio was set to 2 between the two overlaid forcing signals. The found minimum displays a high receptiveness to the frequency f_1 , instead of the sub-harmonic frequency f_2 , where multiple minima can also be found in the upper left plot in Fig. 2. This lower influence of the f_2 frequency can be due to the lower forcing amplitude of f_2 . The phase value, shown in the upper right plot for the overlay of ϕ_2 and f_1 , indicates an overall low influence on the minimum compared to the influence of the f_1 . The variation of parameters clearly shows that the f_1 frequency is the one where the turbulent structure of the round jet for this forcing is the most sensitive, and by slightly changing the frequency, a rapid increase in centerline velocity occurs, peaking at $f_1 \approx 100$ Hz. Also, the A_s has a strong influence on the centerline velocity. For some frequencies, a low amplitude ratio seems to be sufficient to have an influence on the coherent structures. Therefore, these two parameters seem more receptive to variation than the ϕ_2 and f_2 .

2. Overlay of one axial and one helical forcing

A second surrogate model was optimized by superposing an axial ($m_1 = 0$) and a helical ($m_2 = 1$) forcing signal. The overlay of an axial and a helical mode is known to generate blooming jets. Similarly to before, the first three minima found by the surrogate model optimization are displayed in Tab. 3 and discussed in the following.

Nr.	f_1 (Hz)	St_1	f_2 (Hz)	St_2	A_s %	ϕ_2 (deg)	u_{diff}	$u_{\text{diff, exp}}$
2a	74.5	1.2481	23.6	0.3954	15.1	133.9	28.0	22.9
2b	54.4	0.9114	23.6	0.3954	15.0	147.9	27.7	24.5
2c	52.0	0.8712	24.2	0.4054	18.9	225.0	26.6	24.9

Table 3 First three minima obtained from the surrogate model for $m_1 = 0$, $m_2 = 1$ and the corresponding experimental values.

The three minima share approximately the same forcing frequency of $f_2 \approx 24$ Hz for the helical spinning mode m_2 , which is close to the natural frequency of the turbulent jet, which was also found in the previous section for one of the two axial modes. For this forcing mode, with one helical and one axial mode, the amplitude ratio is lower for the forcing of $m_1 = 0$ and higher for the helical forcing mode. The amplitude ratio is divided for the three minima at 15 - 18 % for the axial forcing and 82 - 85 % for the helical forcing. This indicates that for all three minima in this section, the helical mode contains a larger amplitude share than the axial mode. Instead, for the axial spinning mode m_1 , the f_1 values of minima Nr. 2b & Nr. 2c are comparable to the higher amplitude frequency of the overlay of two axial forcings. Indicating that for the axial forcing mode, the best-suited forcing frequency for the turbulent jet at $Re = 10,000$ is approximately 50 Hz. The frequency ratio for the first local minimum Nr. 2a is 3.2 instead, for minima Nr. 2b &

Nr. 2c it is 2.4. For the u_{diff} results of the surrogate model, all three minima result in a significantly lower reduction in centerline velocity compared to the overlay of two axial forcings. As in the previous section, the measured experimental results show lower centerline reduction than the surrogate model ones, which shows that the surrogate model fits the minima with an overestimated centerline velocity. This could be accounted for by increasing the sampling points of the algorithm. However, the algorithm can accurately predict minima. The global minimum of the optimization is displayed in Fig. 3, with a variation of the parameters through the found minimum, to investigate the influence of the two forcing modes.

Fig. 3 Global minimum of the surrogate model for the case of $m_1 = 0, m_2 = 1$ with $\text{Re} = 10,000$ and a maximum forcing of $A_{\text{max}} = 2\%$. The planes are a cut through the minimum that is located at $f_1 = 74.5$ Hz, $f_2 = 23.6$ Hz, $A_s = 15.1\%$, $\phi = 134^\circ$ with a velocity reduction at the centerline of $u_{\text{diff}} = 28\%$.

The identified global minimum of the surrogate model results in a narrower region of receptiveness compared to the results of the previous section. The frequency associated with the higher amplitude is halved, resulting in $f_2 = 23$ Hz, which is the frequency of the axial forcing. This reduction in the dominant frequency amplitude-wise should be due to the helical forcing. The superposed axially forcing frequency is $f_1/f_2 \approx 3.1$ and is in agreement with [13] where the frequency ratio for the blooming jets is approximately 3. As before, the influence of the phase on the found minimum is comparably low. the influence of the axial forcing and its frequency is comparably less responsive than that of the helical forcing. The surrogate model indicates in the center plot of the upper row in Fig. 3 that the supposition of the axial mode is beneficial in reducing of the centerline velocity. This global minimum has a higher centerline velocity

reduction than the overlay of two axial forcings. Nevertheless, from the surrogate model, it can be seen that the region in which the response is achieved is narrowed.

3. Overlay of two counter spinning helical forcings

Last, we optimize a surrogate model based on the response of the jet forced with two counter-spinning helical forcings with $m = \pm 1$. As in the previous sections, the first three minima of the surrogate model are displayed in Tab. 4 and discussed below.

Nr.	f_1 (Hz)	St_1	f_2 (Hz)	St_2	A_s %	ϕ_2 (deg)	u_{diff}	$u_{diff, exp}$
3a	37.8	0.6333	288.6	4.8349	58.7	34.9	29.5	20.5
3b	332.0	5.5620	42.1	0.7053	5.0	307.7	29.4	16.5
3c	30.7	0.5143	32.1	0.5378	67.7	172.8	28.8	20.3

Table 4 First three minima obtained from the surrogate model for $m_1 = -1$, $m_2 = 1$ and the corresponding experimental values.

In contrast to the previous two cases, the three minima deviate significantly from each other. The first minimum Nr. 3a results in the highest centerline reduction both on the surrogate model and experimentally. The frequencies are split with a 59 % to 41 % amplitude ratio, resulting in similar forcing strengths for both forcing signals. The achieved experimental reduction in centerline velocity is slightly lower than the experimentally measured values of the overlay of an axial- and a helical forcing. However, the interplay of the two forcing signals is comparably stronger since the amplitude ratio is closer to the center of the parameter range. The minimum Nr. 3b results in the frequency that shows inverted forcing signals compared to minimum Nr. 3a. This is due to the fact that the parameter space is not constrained, and therefore the same minimum can be found by inverting the forcings. This also indicates that the rotational direction of the helical forcing does not affect the centerline velocity. However, the values for the amplitude ratio for minimum Nr. 3b are at the boundary given to the global minimum search on the surrogate model, set to 5 %. The experimentally determined result shows that the centerline reduction is significantly lower than the other two minima for this case. This indicates that the model precision is not high enough at the boundary, which results in wrong estimations of the minima. The minimum Nr. 3c results in approximately equal forcing frequency, which should generate a flapping motion at a fixed geometry position. This flapping motion could result in the exploitation of the optimization of the precisions in the positioning of the Pitot tube. In the following, the global minimum (Nr. 3a) is further investigated, analogously to the previous section, a variation of the parameters is performed around the global minimum and displayed in Fig. 4.

The resulting global minimum strongly differs from the previously found results. The ratio between the frequencies is much larger, approximately a factor of eight. The amplitude split is close to 60 %. The region found around the minimum depends on both frequencies and is also mirrored on the axis for the second frequency, due to the approximately even split of forcings. The phase has a comparably weak influence on the found minimum, nevertheless, a clear trend

Fig. 4 Global minimum of the surrogate model for the case of $m_1 = -1$, $m_2 = 1$ with $\text{Re} = 10,000$ and a maximum forcing of $A_{\max} = 2\%$. The planes are a cut through the minimum that is located at $f_1 = 37.8$ Hz, $f_2 = 288.6$ Hz, $A_s = 0.587$, $\phi = 34^\circ$ with a velocity reduction at the centerline of $u_{\text{diff}} = 29.5\%$.

towards lower u_{diff} values can be seen for low phase values. To the authors, this result has not yet been reported in the literature. Extensive studies on the overlaying of spinning modes were carried out [31, 32], but the frequencies were matched for a standing wave to generate a flapping mode. The result of this optimization is a global minimum that, to the best of our knowledge, is unknown in the literature. This demonstrates the power of automatized optimization algorithms and the use of surrogate models for investigating high-dimension parameter spaces in experiments. For more detailed information about the influence of the forcing signals on the turbulent jet in the following, some minima are investigated by means of visualization.

B. Investigation of the found minimum by means of flow visualization

To investigate the influence of the forcing scheme determined by the optimization, we visualize the flow using oil droplets generated by an oil seeder (Topas, Aerosol Generator 210). The oil droplets are illuminated by a continuous wave laser (Laser QUANTUM) bundled into a laser sheet at 532 nm. To capture the illumination a high-speed camera (Photron SA-Z) is used. The sampling rate of the camera is set to 5,000 Hz to resolve the shear layer structure for 4.5 seconds. The frame size is chosen to fit seven diameters on the y-axis and ± 2 diameters on the x-axis. This is chosen to capture the intensity up to the measurement point of the Pitot tube used for the optimization. To further investigate the

results, a comparison to the unforced jet is taken. The visualization of the turbulent jet gives a qualitative insight into the mean field of the turbulent jet and the coherent structures. A physical quantification of this data is unfortunately unfeasible since the spatially resolved values display light intensity, which is related to the amount of oil droplets and not to a physical quantity such as pressure or velocity. A further drawback is that the light is absorbed by the seeding which results in a slight asymmetry in the mean fields due to the reduced light intensity on the side of the turbulent jet further away from the light source.

Fig. 5 Mean fields of the light intensity from the turbulent jet. The values are displayed for the unforced case and three exemplary minima. The outlet diameter of the jet D normalizes the axis.

The mean values for the unforced jet, for two minima from the overlay of two helical modes, and for the minimum found by the overlay of an axial and a helical mode are displayed in Fig. 5. The unforced jet light intensity ends at $6.5 y/D$, with an increased light intensity within the potential core. The jet shows asymmetries in the region between the x -axis at $y/D \in [2, 4]$. This may be due to the lack of light intensity on the opposite side, due to the seeding absorbing the light. The found minima for the three configurations reduce the length of the light intensity. Resulting in a compacter jet shape, with a reduction in light intensity $5.8 y/D$. The minimum Nr. 3a results in a slightly thickened jet base at $y/D \approx 1.5$. What differentiates the minimum Nr. 3a is that one of the frequencies is significantly higher than the other, in comparison to the further displayed minima. The bump at the jet base could be due to the influence of this high frequency. The minimum Nr. 3c results in a symmetric mean field with a shortened light distribution. The minimum Nr. 2a, which is a result of one axial and one helical forcing, results in a reduced jet length, which however results in a higher light intensity at $3-4 y/D$, compared to the other two found minima.

To visualize the coherent structures of the turbulent jet, single snapshots are displayed, these are taken at $1/5000$ of a second and are shown in Fig. 6. The snapshot of the unforced jet results in a symmetric coherent structure, with vortices paired at the same y -axis position. The main light intensity is on the center line between $2-4 y/D$ for the unforced condition. The highest light intensity (green color) region is centered and close to symmetry. Instead for the found minimum Nr. 3a, the centerline in the region with the highest light intensity is forced into a flapping motion. The

Fig. 6 Single snap shoots of the light intensity from the turbulent jet. The values are displayed for the unforced case and three exemplary minima. The outlet diameter of the jet normalizes the axis.

vortices reflect this flapping motion, they are ordered asymmetrically at the exit of the turbulent jet. For the minimum Nr. 3c, the vortices at the base of the flow are also asymmetric. However, the highest intensity of the light is distributed closer to the center axis. The minimum Nr. 2a, containing a helical and an axial mode, is closer to the symmetries of the vortices, however on the snapshot, the negative x-axis displays a large vortex roll-up, this is due to the rotating forcing, and should only be due to the snap shoot. The light is concentrated closer to the jet centerline.

The visualization shows that the optimization goal of a higher turbulent mixing is achieved by the automated optimization routine. For all three investigated minima, the influence of the forcing results in a reduction of jet length. The minima display differing coherent structures that, for further insight into the physics, need to be investigated, e.g., by using PIV to gain quantitative information on the velocity profiles.

V. Conclusion

In this work, we studied the response of a turbulent jet to an azimuthally distributed forcing actuated by 8 loudspeakers. The forcing signal was constructed as the superposition of two harmonic signals with different amplitudes, azimuthal numbers, frequencies, and phases. The response of the jet was studied by sampling the parameter space and constructing a surrogate model that was iteratively improved by means of an automated algorithm. At each iterative step, a search on the surrogate model was performed, to identify the point in parameter space yielding results with the highest prediction uncertainty. Then, a measurement was taken at this candidate point. For each of the surrogate models presented in this work, 750 iterations were performed. The parameter space that is covered is four-dimensional. The resulting surrogate models are used to find their corresponding global minimum. This global minimum is then further investigated. We can approximately reproduce known values from the literature, such as the optimality of sub-harmonic forcings for axisymmetric jets and blooming jets. The parameter space to investigate is very extensive, and many studies performed in the past were limited to special cases that, e.g., related the superposed frequencies by integer factors. In this work, we

relaxed these constraints and we present a newfound solution to minimize the entrainment of the jet by an uncoupled counter-spinning helical forcing, which results in a slight reduction of the jet's velocity on the centerline than the superposition of an axial and a helical forcing, which are assumed to be a blooming jet. With a frequency ratio of eight and a quasi-even amplitude split of the forcings, this global minimum has not been reported before. For a quantitative analysis of the found minima, flow visualizations are performed. These show that the scope of the optimization to reduce the jet length is achieved. Further, the visualization shows that the overlay of two frequencies for the found minima with helical forcings breaks the symmetric structure of the unforced jet. This unknown global solution to the control of a turbulent jet demonstrates how using automated experiments in combination with surrogate models can lead to an accurate prediction of the global minimum. Furthermore, the method can predict local minima on the surrogate model and give a good insight into the influence of the input variables on the perceptiveness of the minimum.

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References

- [1] Goldstein, S., *Modern developments in fluid dynamics: an account of theory and experiment relating to boundary layers, turbulent motion and wakes*, Vol. 2, Clarendon Press, 1938.
- [2] Krebs, W., Schulz, A., Witzel, B., Johnson, C., Laster, W., Pent, J., Schilp, R., Wasif, S., and Weaver, A., "Advanced Combustion System for High Efficiency (ACE) of the New SGT5/6- 9000HL Gas Turbine," *Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, Vol. Volume 3B: Combustion, Fuels, and Emissions, 2022, p. V03BT04A018. <https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2022-82299>, URL <https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2022-82299>.
- [3] Crow, S. C., and Champagne, F. H., "Orderly structure in jet turbulence," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 48, 1971, pp. 547–591. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112071001745>.
- [4] Cohen, J., and Wygnanski, I., "The evolution of instabilities in the axisymmetric jet. part 1. the linear growth of disturbances near the nozzle," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 176, 1987, pp. 191–219. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112087000624>.
- [5] Samimy, M., Webb, N., and Crawley, M., "Excitation of free shear-layer instabilities for high-speed flow control," *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 56, 2018, pp. 1770–1791. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.J056610>.
- [6] Michalke, A., "On spatially growing disturbances in an inviscid shear layer," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 23, 1965, pp. 521–544. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112065001520>.

- [7] Boguslawski, A., Wawrzak, K., and Tyliczszak, A., “A new insight into understanding the Crow and Champagne preferred mode: a numerical study,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 869, 2019, pp. 385–416. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2019.220>.
- [8] Cohen, J., and Wignanski, “The evolution of instabilities in the axisymmetric jet. part 2. the flow resulting from the interaction between two waves,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 176, 1987, pp. 221–235. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112087000636>.
- [9] Michalke, A., “Survey on jet instability theory,” *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, Vol. 21, 1984, pp. 159–199. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0376-0421\(84\)90005-8](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0376-0421(84)90005-8), URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/0376042184900058>.
- [10] Paschereit, C. O., Oster, D., Long, T. A., Fiedler, H. E., and Wignanski, I., “Flow visualization of interactions among large coherent structures in an axisymmetric jet,” *Experiments in Fluids*, Vol. 12, No. 3, 1992, pp. 189–199. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00188258>, URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/BF00188258>.
- [11] Long, T. A., and Petersen, R. A., “Controlled interactions in a forced axisymmetric jet. Part 1. The distortion of the mean flow,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 235, No. -1, 1992, p. 37. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112092001010>, URL http://www.journals.cambridge.org/abstract_S0022112092001010.
- [12] Paschereit, C. O., Wignanski, I., and Fiedler, H. E., “Experimental investigation of subharmonic resonance in an axisymmetric jet,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 283, 1995, pp. 365–407. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112095002369>, URL https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0022112095002369/type/journal_article.
- [13] Reynolds, W. C., Parekh, D. E., Juvet, P. J. D., and Lee, M. J. D., “Bifurcation and Blooming Jets,” *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 35, No. 1, 2003, pp. 295–315. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.fluid.35.101101.161128>, URL <https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/10.1146/annurev.fluid.35.101101.161128>.
- [14] Hilgers, A., and Boersma, B., “Optimization of turbulent jet mixing,” *Fluid dynamics research*, Vol. 29, No. 6, 2001, p. 345.
- [15] Koumoutsakos, P., Freund, J., and Parekh, D., “Evolution strategies for automatic optimization of jet mixing,” *AIAA Journal*, Vol. 39, 2001, pp. 967–969. <https://doi.org/10.2514/2.1404>.
- [16] Wu, Z., Fan, D., Zhou, Y., Li, R., and Noack, B. R., “Jet mixing optimization using machine learning control,” *Experiments in Fluids*, Vol. 59, No. 8, 2018, p. 131. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00348-018-2582-4>, URL <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00348-018-2582-4>.
- [17] Zhou, Y., Zhou, Y., Fan, D., Zhang, B., Li, R., Li, R., Noack, B. R., Noack, B. R., and Noack, B. R., “Artificial intelligence control of a turbulent jet,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2020.392>.
- [18] Ren, F., bao Hu, H., and Tang, H., “Active flow control using machine learning: A brief review,” *Journal of Hydrodynamics*, Vol. 32, 2020, pp. 247–253. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42241-020-0026-0>, URL <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s42241-020-0026-0>.

- [19] Sengupta, U., and Juniper, M. P., “Thermoacoustic stabilization of combustors with gradient-augmented Bayesian optimization and adjoint models,” *International Journal of Spray and Combustion Dynamics*, Vol. 14, No. 3-4, 2022, pp. 266–272. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17568277221109118>, URL <https://doi.org/10.1177/17568277221109118>.
- [20] Krige, D. G., “A statistical approach to some basic mine valuation problems on the Witwatersrand,” *Journal of the Southern African Institute of Mining and Metallurgy*, Vol. 52, 1951, pp. 119–139. URL http://journals.co.za/content/saimm/52/6/AJA0038223X_4792.
- [21] Rasmussen, C. E., and Williams, C. K. I., *Gaussian processes in machine learning*, 5, the MIT Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, 2006. URL www.GaussianProcess.org/gpml.
- [22] Jones, D. R., Schonlau, M., and Welch, W. J., “Efficient Global Optimization of Expensive Black-Box Functions,” *Journal of Global Optimization*, Vol. 13, No. 4, 1998, pp. 455–492. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008306431147>, URL <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1008306431147>.
- [23] Srinivas, N., Krause, A., Kakade, S. M., and Seeger, M., “Gaussian process optimization in the bandit setting: No regret and experimental design,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:0912.3995*, 2009.
- [24] Endres, S. C., Sandrock, C., and Focke, W. W., “shgo: Simplicial homology global optimisation,” *SoftwareX*, 2018, pp. 1–16. URL <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:221779451>.
- [25] Oberleithner, K., Paschereit, C. O., and Wagnanski, I., “On the impact of swirl on the growth of coherent structures,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 741, 2014, pp. 156–199. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2013.669>, URL https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0022112013006691/type/journal_article.
- [26] Bouhleb, M. A., Hwang, J. T., Bartoli, N., Lafage, R., Morlier, J., and Martins, J. R., “A Python surrogate modeling framework with derivatives,” *Advances in Engineering Software*, Vol. 135, 2019, p. 102662. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advengsoft.2019.03.005>, URL <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0965997818309360>.
- [27] Sacks, J., Schiller, S. B., and Welch, W. J., “Designs for Computer Experiments,” *Technometrics*, Vol. 31, No. 1, 1989, pp. 41–47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00401706.1989.10488474>, URL <http://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00401706.1989.10488474>.
- [28] McKay, M. D., Beckman, R. J., and Conover, W. J., “A comparison of three methods for selecting values of input variables in the analysis of output from a computer code,” *Technometrics*, Vol. 42, No. 1, 2000, pp. 55–61. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00401706.2000.10485979>.
- [29] Gelb, A., and Velde, W. E. V., *Multiple-Input Describing Functions and Nonlinear System Design*, McGraw-Hill, 1968.
- [30] Crow, S. C., and Champagne, F. H., “Orderly structure in jet turbulence,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 48, No. 3, 1971, pp. 547–591. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112071001745>, URL https://www.cambridge.org/core/product/identifier/S0022112071001745/type/journal_article.

- [31] Cohen, J., and Wygnanski, I., "The evolution of instabilities in the axisymmetric jet. Part 2. The flow resulting from the interaction between two waves," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 176, No. -1, 1987, p. 221. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112087000636>, URL http://www.journals.cambridge.org/abstract_S0022112087000636.
- [32] Cohen, J., and Wygnanski, I., "The evolution of instabilities in the axisymmetric jet. Part 1. The linear growth of disturbances near the nozzle," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, Vol. 176, No. -1, 1987, p. 191. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112087000624>, URL http://www.journals.cambridge.org/abstract_S0022112087000624.